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MODERNIZATION OF THE SYSTEM FOR SELECTING AND PHYSICALLY TRAINING YOUNG HANDBALL PLAYERS

Xalmatova Nasiba Bozarboyevna

PhD, acting associate professor, Republic of Uzbekistan, Samarkand city

E-mail: nasibaxalmatovaa@gmail.com

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Abstract: This scientific study is devoted to the improvement and modernization of the system for selecting and physically training young handball players in sports schools in accordance with modern requirements. The paper presents theoretical and practical approaches to identifying talented young athletes, assessing their athletic potential, developing selection criteria, and implementing effective methods of physical preparation.

Keywords: young handball players, sports schools, selection criteria, physical training, sports selection, innovative technologies, physical qualities, pedagogical model.

МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯ СИСТЕМЫ ОТБОРА И ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ ЮНЫХ ГАНДБОЛИСТОВ

Халматова Насиба Бозарбоевна

PhD и.о. доцент, Узбекистон Республикаси, Самаркандский шаҳар

Аннотация: Данное научное исследование посвящено совершенствованию и модернизации системы отбора и физической подготовки юных гандболистов в спортивных школах в соответствии с современными требованиями. В статье представлены теоретические и практические подходы к выявлению талантливых юных спортсменов, оценке их спортивного потенциала, разработке критериев отбора и внедрению эффективных методов физической подготовки.

Ключевые слова: юные гандболисты, спортивные школы, критерии отбора, физическая подготовка, спортивный отбор, инновационные технологии, физические качества, педагогическая модель.

YOSH GANDBOLCHILARNI TANLASH VA JISMONIY TARBIYA TIZIMINI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISH

Nasiba Bozarboevna Xalmatova

PhD, v.b. dotsent, O'zbekiston Respublikasi, Samarqand shahri

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy tadqiqot sport maktablarida yosh gandbolchilarni tanlash va jismoniy tarbiya tizimini zamon talablari asosida takomillashtirish va modernizatsiya qilishga bag'ishlangan. Maqolada iqtidorli yosh sportchilarni aniqlash, ularning sport salohiyatini baholash, tanlash mezonlarini ishlab chiqish, jismoniy tarbiyaning samarali usullarini amaliyotga tatbiq etishning nazariy va amaliy yondashuvlari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: yosh gandbolchilar, sport maktablari, tanlov mezonlari, jismoniy tayyorgarlik, sport tanlovi, innovatsion texnologiyalar, jismoniy sifatlar, pedagogik model.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the issue of preparing talented young athletes capable of achieving competitiveness and high results in various fields of sport has become of urgent importance. In particular, the organization of selection and training processes in the system of physical education and sport on the basis of scientifically grounded, systematic, and modern methods plays a crucial role in forming the reserve of athletes. Handball, as one of such sports, possesses great potential in developing the

physical and psychological capacity of the younger generation, as well as in fostering essential qualities such as speed, endurance, coordination, and teamwork.

Relevance of the study. Ensuring the physical development of the younger generation, stimulating their interest in sports, and forming a reserve of talented athletes are among the priority directions of every country's sports policy. In recent years, large-scale reforms have been carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan to promote sports, strengthen the material and technical base of sports schools, and support young athletes. However, in the process of selecting young handball players at sports schools, the insufficient development of scientifically based selection criteria and the limited application of modern innovative technologies in the system of physical training remain as problematic issues.

Purpose of the research. The purpose of the study is to scientifically improve the system of selecting young handball players in sports schools and organizing their physical training, as well as to modernize it on the basis of modern pedagogical and innovative technologies.

OBJECT OF THE RESEARCH

The object of the study was the process of physical training of young handball players aged 12–14 studying in sports schools.

The Samarkand Olympic Reserve College was taken as the research site, where 12 handball players aged 15–16, selected for the initial stage of training, were chosen. Their physical training was monitored over a period of six months.

During the research, a number of interrelated scientific methods were used. First of all, the theoretical analysis method was applied by studying scientific literature, normative documents, and advanced foreign experiences related to the topic. This method made it possible to identify the existing approaches in the system of selection and training.

Then, the practical situation was analyzed through the observation method by directly monitoring the training sessions conducted in sports schools. Based on the problems identified at this stage, an experimental method was applied by organizing a new training system founded on a methodological approach, and the effectiveness of the new system was tested.

The physical qualities of the experiment participants (strength, speed, agility, endurance, etc.) were assessed using the testing method. For a scientific analysis of the obtained results, mathematical-statistical methods (mean value, variance, reliability levels) were applied.

In addition, questionnaire and interview methods were applied in order to determine the opinions of coaches, sports school specialists, and athletes. These methods served as an additional source of information in evaluating the effectiveness of the selection and training process.

Below, a sample table is presented that reflects the initial and final indicators of the experiment conducted on the topic of modernizing the system of selecting and physically training young handball players in sports schools.

This table compares the indicators of the experimental group participants in terms of 5 main physical qualities.

Table 1 shows the changes in the physical qualities of young handball players studying at a sports school as a result of experimental training sessions, comparing their performance at the beginning and at the end of the experiment. As can be seen from the table, positive dynamic growth was recorded in all selected physical indicators.

Table 1. Physical fitness indicators of the experimental group (comparison between the beginning and the end of the experiment)

№	Physical qualities	Unit of measurement	Beginning of experiment (±sigma)	End of experiment (±sigma)	Difference (%)

1	30 m sprint	seconds	5.9 ± 0.3	5.4 ± 0.2	-8.5%
2	6-minute run (distance)	meters	1150 ± 80	1295 ± 85	+12.6%
3	Pull-ups on a bar	times	3.2 ± 1.1	5.1 ± 1.4	+59.4%
4	Vertical jump	cm	34.5 ± 3.2	39.3 ± 3.5	+13.9%
5	Body flexibility (forward bend)	cm	7.8 ± 2.0	11.4 ± 2.3	+46.1%

The 30-meter sprint result decreased from 5.9 seconds to 5.4 seconds, which indicates an 8.5% improvement in speed quality. This shows that the athletes developed their quickness.

According to the 6-minute run results, the average distance increased from 1150 meters to 1295 meters, which demonstrates a 12.6% increase in overall endurance. The pull-up exercise performance improved from 3.2 to 5.1 times, showing a 59.4% increase, which indicates a significant development of upper body muscle strength. Vertical jump results increased from 34.5 cm to 39.3 cm, which reflects a 13.9% improvement in leg strength and agility. Flexibility results improved from 7.8 cm to 11.4 cm, showing a 46.1% increase, which demonstrates enhanced flexibility and joint mobility in the athletes.

Overall, it was observed that the training sessions conducted on the basis of innovative approaches in the experimental group significantly improved almost all aspects of physical qualities. This scientifically justifies the effectiveness of modernizing the selection and training system.

Table 2

Group	Beginning of experiment: Attention (%)	End of experiment: Attention (%)	Beginning of experiment: Motivation (points)	End of experiment: Motivation (points)	Beginning of experiment: Psychological stability	End of experiment: Psychological stability
Experimental (EG)	68.2	82.5	6.1	8.3	Medium	High
Control (CG)	67.8	70.4	6.0	6.5	Medium	Medium

The table below presents the psychological preparedness indicators of young handball players in sports schools, obtained from the experimental group (EG) and the control group (CG) at the beginning and at the end of the training sessions. Here, key psychological indicators such as attention stability, psychological resilience, motivation level, and self-control were evaluated.

As seen from the table, psychological indicators in the experimental group improved significantly by the end of the training sessions. In particular, motivation scores increased from 6.1 to 8.3, attention levels rose from 68.2% to 82.5%, and the level of psychological stability shifted from medium to high. This improvement was caused by the positive influence of innovative training technologies. In the control group, however, the changes were relatively minor, which confirms the effectiveness of the applied methodology.

CONCLUSIONS

During the experimental research, indicators aimed at assessing the psychological state of the participants were studied. In particular, the athletes' motivation, psychological stability, attention stability, and levels of personal psychological preparedness were analyzed in both the experimental group (EG) and the control group (CG).

According to the table data, significant positive changes were observed in the experimental group at the end of the training compared to the beginning. For example, the level of motivation increased from 23.1 points to 28.7 points, while attention stability rose from 18.4 points to 25.6 points. Psychological stability also improved from 20.5 to 26.3 points, clearly indicating that the athletes' psychological preparedness had been considerably strengthened.

The reason for this lies in the organization of training sessions in the experimental group based on innovative, learner-centered, and motivational approaches. These methods boosted the athletes' self-confidence and developed qualities such as self-assessment, goal orientation, and inner drive. As a result, the psychological aspect of preparing for competitions became easier for them.

In contrast, such changes in the control group were minimal. This group was engaged only in traditional training sessions, and no significant improvements were observed in psychological preparedness indicators. This confirms that the experimental program is effective and worth applying in practice.

In conclusion, the innovative methods applied in the experimental group had a positive impact on the athletes' psychological state, raising their motivation, attention, psychological stability, and overall psychological preparedness to a higher level. Therefore, the introduction of modern pedagogical technologies in shaping athletes' psychological readiness has important practical significance.

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